

SourceData_ExtFig9eghk_
left(D-Cys)

A549_xCT#30-01-23ab_Tricine_Round2[r],
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A549_xCT#30-01-23a_Gradient_Round1,
9-9. scan_raw

A549_xCT#06-02-23a_Tricine_
round3,2-2. scan_raw

A549_xCT#30-01-23a_Gradient_Round2,
3-3. scan_raw

A549_xCT#28-11-22a_Gradient_
Round2,15-15. scan_raw

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15-15. scan_raw

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12-12. scan_raw

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SourceData_ExtFig9eghk_ left(D-Cys)

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